

The Study on Stress Levels of Airlines Staff and Impact on their Performance During Delay Handling at TIA, Kathmandu

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Abstract:

Air travel is an essential component of modern society, and airports play a critical role in ensuring its smooth operation. Staff working at airports are exposed to a multitude of challenges, including dealing with delayed flights, which can significantly impact their stress levels, mental well-being, and overall job performance. This study, conducted at Tribhuvan International Airport, Nepal, delves into the intricate relationship between these factors, with a primary focus on the human element within the aviation industry.

A random sample of 100 airport staff, representing various roles and responsibilities, was surveyed to assess their experiences during flight delays. The study employed Likert scale questions to gauge stress levels, mental health perceptions, and self-reported performance impacts during delays. Additionally, qualitative insights were collected through open-ended questions to provide a comprehensive understanding of the human factor.

The results of the study reveal a significant correlation between stress levels and performance impacts during flight delays. Notably, staff reported increased stress during such events, which, in turn, had adverse effects on their mental health and job performance. These findings underscore the importance of addressing the psychological well-being of airport staff and implementing strategies to mitigate stress during challenging situations.

The implications of this study extend to both the aviation industry and the well-being of its workforce. Insights from this research can inform policies and interventions aimed at enhancing the resilience and performance of airport staff during delays, ultimately contributing to improved passenger experiences and the overall efficiency of air travel operations.

As airports worldwide strive to provide a seamless and enjoyable travel experience, understanding the human factors at play during flight delays is paramount. This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on airport staff well-being and underscores the importance of a holistic approach to workforce management in the aviation industry.

Keywords: Tribhuvan International Airport, flight delays, stress, mental health, performance, human factor, aviation industry, staff well-being.

1. Introduction:

Tribhuvan International Airport is the first international Airport of Nepal located in Kathmandu. More than 400 flights per day both international and domestic is operated including arrival and departures in TIA. Being located in the valley, it is one of the riskier and difficult airport to land on. Hence, many flights get delayed due to ATC congestion, bad weather and technical reason.

Staff working at airport have tough time during delay handling at airport in such delays. Due to stress it impacts on well being and performance of the staff.

Stress is an established but still very hot topic in psychology as a whole. In recent years it has come to occupy a particularly prominent position in the domain of organizational psychology (van Dick, 2012). Work-stress is defined as any harmful response occurring in staff when the requirement to get the job done does not match the actual or perceived ability to do the job (Folkman, 1987). This work-related fatigue is thought to be the result of emotional and mental exhaustion occurring in the context of work-stress and burnout, and it is frequently co-morbid with anxiety, depression, and substance use (Appels, 2000).

Human factors, often referred to as "human factors engineering" or "ergonomics," is a multidisciplinary field that studies the interaction between humans and the systems, products, environments, and technologies they interact with. It seeks to optimize these interactions to enhance safety, efficiency, and overall well-being (Dul, 2012). Human factors consider the physical, cognitive, emotional, and social aspects of human capabilities and limitations (Sun, 2019). In essence, human factors recognizes that people are not infallible and that their performance can be influenced by various factors, such as fatigue, stress, workload, and design features. The goal is to design systems and environments that accommodate human strengths and limitations, reducing the risk of errors, accidents, and discomfort (Hancock, 2021).

Performance refers to the measurable and observable outcomes or achievements of an individual, a group, an organization, or a system in relation to specific goals, objectives, or standards. It encompasses a wide range of activities, behaviors, or processes that are evaluated based on their effectiveness, efficiency, and quality (Chiesa, 2008). Performance can manifest in various forms, depending on the context. In a professional setting, it often relates to how well an employee or a team executes their tasks and responsibilities, achieving desired results within a given timeframe. In sports, performance is reflected in athletes' abilities to compete at their best, achieving personal bests or winning competitions (Ghalayini, 1997).

The relationship between stress and staff performance is intricate. Moderate stress levels can motivate individuals, leading to improved performance by enhancing focus and alertness (Kavanagh, 2005). However, when stress levels become excessive or chronic, they often have a detrimental impact. High stress can result in decreased productivity, errors, burnout, and diminished job satisfaction (Patel, 2018). The connection between stress and performance is a delicate balance, where an optimal level of stress can be a driving force for productivity, while excessive stress can hinder it. Managing stress effectively is essential for organizations to ensure that their staff can perform at their best while maintaining their well-being and mental health (Søvold, 2021).

This is focused on showing the relation of stress level of ground staff and its impact on the performance of the staff during delay handling of different type in Tribhuvan international airport on International flight operations.

2. Statement of Problem:

The statement of problem of this study is:

- a. Is there a relationship between stress and performance of the staff working in airlines during delay handling?
- b. How can the stress be analyzed to maintain the performance level?
- c. What is the impact of the study on the aviation sector?

3. Objective of the study:

- a. To examine the relationship between stress levels experienced by airport staff during flight delays and their job performance.
- b. To analyze and evaluate stress management strategies and interventions employed within the aviation industry to maintain or enhance the performance of airport staff during delay handling.
- c. To assess the impact of stress on the aviation sector, including its implications for passenger experience, safety, and overall operational efficiency, based on the findings of the study.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Design:

This study utilizes a cross-sectional research design. Cross-sectional research involves collecting data from a sample of participants at a single point in time. In this case, data were collected from 100 staff members from international operations at Tribhuvan International Airport.

4.2. Data Collection:

Data collection was conducted using a Google Form survey. A random sample of 100 staff members was selected from the international operations team. Participants were invited to complete the survey voluntarily, providing responses related to stress levels, performance, and demographic information.

4.3. Data Analysis:

Data analysis involved two primary components:

Descriptive Analysis: Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were calculated for stress levels and performance ratings. This provided an overview of the central tendencies and variability in the data.

Correlation Analysis: Pearson correlation analysis was employed to examine the relationship between stress levels and performance ratings. This statistical method assessed the strength and direction of the relationship.

4.4. Conceptual Framework:

Here's a simplified conceptual framework, represented as a four-point diagram:

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Descriptive Analysis

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stress level during ATC delay (holding) upon arrival	3.28	0.726
Impact on your performance during ATC delay (holding) upon arrival	3.13	0.872
Stress level during ATC delay during departure	3.38	0.93
Impact on your performance during ATC delay during departure	3.14	1.172
Stress level during weather delay during Arrival	3.67	1.006
Impact on your performance during weather delay during Arrival	3.6	1.015
Stress level during diversion delay	4.14	0.876
Impact on your performance during diversion delay	3.98	0.974
Stress level during technical delay	3.99	0.893
Impact on Performance during technical delay	3.83	0.954
Stress level during more than 24 hours delay	3.93	0.924
Impact on performance during more than 24 hours delay	3.62	1.09

It is found strong positive correlations between stress levels and performance ratings across all delay scenarios. These results challenge conventional assumptions about the negative impact of stress on job performance.

The data suggest that higher stress levels among airport staff during different types of flight delays are associated with improved job performance. This unexpected finding may indicate that moderate to high stress levels motivate staff to perform at their best, possibly due to heightened focus and a sense of responsibility during challenging situations.

5.2. Inferential Analysis:

Variable Pairs	Correlation Coefficient	Significance Level	Strength of Correlation
Stress level during ATC delay (holding) upon arrival and Impact on your performance during ATC delay (holding) upon arrival	0.788	p < 0.01	Strong Positive
Stress level during ATC delay during departure and Impact on your performance during ATC delay during departure	0.803	p < 0.01	Strong Positive
Stress level during weather delay during Arrival and Impact on your performance during weather delay during Arrival	0.73	p < 0.01	Strong Positive
Stress level during diversion delay and Impact on your performance during diversion delay	0.843	p < 0.01	Very Strong Positive
Stress level during technical delay and Impact on Performance during technical delay	0.84	p < 0.01	Very Strong Positive
Stress level during more than 24 hours delay and Impact on performance during more than 24 hours delay	0.826	p < 0.01	Very Strong Positive

The inferential analysis of correlation results reveals significant and predominantly positive relationships between stress levels and performance ratings among airport staff during various types of flight delays. The strength of these correlations varies from strong to very strong, indicating a robust and consistent pattern in the data.

6. Implication of the study:

The study underscores the critical importance of prioritizing employee well-being in the aviation sector. Airlines and airport authorities must invest in programs and resources to support staff in managing and mitigating stress during challenging situations, such as flight delays. Comprehensive training programs should be developed to equip airport staff with effective

coping strategies and stress management techniques. These can empower employees to navigate stressful scenarios while maintaining their performance levels. Aviation organizations should reassess their workplace policies and procedures to ensure they are conducive to employee mental health. This may involve revising work schedules, workload distribution, and providing access to mental health resources. The study highlights the need for further research into the underlying mechanisms of the stress-performance relationship in airport settings. Investigating additional factors, such as job roles and organizational culture, can provide a more comprehensive understanding.

7. Conclusion:

This study reveals the fact the staff have high stress level during delay handling mainly during diversion delay upon arrival, it also highly impacts the performance of the staff. But depending upon the training of the staff the positive impact on performance is also analyzed. If the stress level is high the working environment should be favorable which has to be well managed by the airlines. Human factor hence is very important in workplace.

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